

A Multi-Functional Heterogeneous Biocatalyst for the Oxygen-Free Oxidative Condensation of Primary Alcohols into β -Hydroxy Acids

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Abbreviations

2,3-DHBA 2,3-dihydroxybutyric acid
2M3HBA 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyric acid
2M3HPA 2-methyl-3-hydroxypentanoic acid
3,4-DHBA 3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid
3-HBA 3-hydroxybutyrate
3-HBA-CoA 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA
3-HPA 3-hydroxypentanoic acid
ΔNPduP N-terminal truncated version of CoA-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase from *Salmonella enterica*
β-BOX Reverse β-oxidation pathway
ADH Alcohol dehydrogenase
AG Crosslinked agarose microbeads
AG-Co²⁺ Agarose functionalized with Cobalt chelates groups
AG-Co²⁺/G/A Agarose functionalized with Cobalt chelates, aldehydes, and amine groups
AG-G Agarose functionalized with glyoxyl groups
AG-PAH Agarose functionalized with polyallylamine
AG-PEI Agarose functionalized with polyethyleneimine
Alexa Alexa Fluor 647 NHS ester
AsAcat5 Thiolase 5 from *Ascaris suum*
ATP Adenosine 5'-triphosphate
Atto Atto 390 NHS ester
BsADH Alcohol dehydrogenase from *Bacillus stearothermophilus*
BsGDH: Thermostable variant of glucose dehydrogenase from *Bacillus subtilis*
CLSM confocal laser scanning microscopy
CoA Coenzyme A
DTNB (Ellman's Reagent) (5,5-dithio-bis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid)
DTT Dithiothreitol
EAA Ethyl acetoacetate
EcTesB Thioesterase B from *Escherichia coli*
Ee Enantiomeric excess
FAD⁺ Flavin adenine dinucleotide
FITC Fluorescein isothiocyanate
GC/MS Gas chromatography coupled to mass spectroscopy
HB Heterogeneous biocatalyst
HPLC: High-performance liquid chromatography
IPTG Isopropyl β-D-thiogalactoside
LB Luria broth
NaBH₄ Sodium borohydride
HisTag Histidine tag
NADH Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (reduced form)
NAD⁺ Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (oxidized form)
NADPH Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (reduced form)
NADP⁺ Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (oxidized form)
NOX NADH oxidase
PAH Poly(allylamine)
PBR Packed-bed reactor
PduP CoA-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase
PEI Poly(ethyleneimine)
ReTHL Thiolase from *Ralstonia eutropha*
RhB Rhodamine B isothiocyanate
SePduP CoA-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase from *Salmonella enterica*
ScADH Alcohol dehydrogenase from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*
STY Space time yield
TB Terrific Broth
TCEP Tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine
THBA 2,3,4-trihydroxybutyric acid
TtHBDH 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase from *Thermus thermophilus*
TTN Turnover number
UPLC/MS Ultra high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectroscopy
WT Wild type

Supplementary methods

Protein expression and purification

Cells containing pET28b-SePduP were grown using LB media supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin at 37 °C and 200 rpm until OD₆₀₀ 0.6 to 0.8, then cooled down to 21 °C, induced with 1 mM IPTG, and incubated for 4 hours.

Cells containing pET28b- Δ NPduP were grown using LB media supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin at 37 °C and 200 rpm until OD₆₀₀ 0.6 to 0.8, then cooled down to 21 °C, induced with 1 mM of IPTG, and incubated for 16 hours.

Cells containing pET28b-BsADH, pET28b-TtHBDH, and pET28b-ReTHL were grown using LB media supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin at 37 °C and 200 rpm until OD₆₀₀ 0.6 to 0.8, then induced with 1 mM of IPTG and incubated for 4 hours.

Cells containing pET28b-LpNOX and pET28b-BsGDH were grown using autoinduction ZY media supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin at 21 °C and 200 rpm for 20 hours.

Cells containing pET28b-AsTHL5 were grown using Terrific Broth (TB) media supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin at 37 °C and 200 rpm until OD₆₀₀ 0.8 to 1, then cooled down to 21 °C, induced with 0.2 mM of IPTG, and incubated for 16 hours as previously described.¹

Cells containing pET28b-EcTesB were grown using Terrific Broth (TB) media supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin at 37 °C and 200 rpm until OD₆₀₀ 0.6 to 0.8, then induced with 0.4 mM of IPTG and incubated for 4 hours as previously described.¹

In all cases, cells were harvested upon induction by centrifugation at 4000 x g, and the pellets were stored for further enzyme purification at -20 °C.

Frozen pellets of His-tagged SePduP, Δ NPduP, AsTHL5, EcTesB, ReTHL, BsADH, LpNOX, and BsGDH were thawed and resuspended in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, 200 mM NaCl, and 10 mM imidazole at pH 7.4. The cell suspension was sonicated in pulses of 5 seconds ON/OFF in a Sonicator Sonopuls HD 4100 (amplitude 20%) for 20 minutes at 4 °C. Cell debris was discarded by centrifugation at 14,000 x g for 20 minutes at 4 °C, and soluble crude extract was loaded into a cobalt-activated agarose resin and incubated in batch for 1 hour at 4 °C under gentle stirring. Next, the resin with the bound enzyme was washed with the previous buffer, and the enzymes were finally eluted with elution buffer, 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, 200 mM NaCl, and 500 mM imidazole at pH 7. SePduP was purified with a similar protocol, but with gravity instead of batch incubation.

TtHBDH pellet was resuspended in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 7 and purified by thermal shock at 70 °C for 45 minutes as described elsewhere.²

All purified enzymes were kept at 4 °C and used on the following days. The purity degree of each protein was analyzed by SDS-PAGE and quantified by Bradford assay.

Enzymatic activity assays

AsTHL5 and *ReTHL*: non-descarboxylative Claisen condensation activity was measured following the protocol described by Blaisse et al.,^{1, 3} Briefly, the corresponding thiolase was mixed with a reaction mixture that contained 1 mM Acetyl-CoA, 0.6 mM (5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB), and 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8. The activity was monitored spectrophotometrically, measuring the release of 2-nitro-5-mercapto-benzoic acid, which has an extinction coefficient of 13.6 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 412 nm. 1 enzyme unit is defined as the amount of enzyme needed to produce 1 μmol of CoA (= 1 μmol of 2-nitro-5-mercapto-benzoic acid) per minute under the above-described conditions.

EcTesB: The corresponding amount of EcTesB was incubated with a reaction mixture that contained 0.2 mM 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA or acetyl-CoA and 0.6 mM DTNB in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8. The hydrolytic activity was monitored spectrophotometrically by measuring the release of 2-nitro-5-mercapto-benzoic acid. 1 enzyme unit (U) is defined as the amount of enzyme needed to produce 1 μmol of CoA (= 1 μmol of 2-nitro-5-mercapto-benzoic acid) per minute under the above-described conditions.

Redox activities of oxidoreductases were followed by measuring either the increase (oxidative direction) or decrease (reductive direction) of absorbance at 340 nm due to the production or depletion of NADH (extinction coefficient of 6.22 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 340 nm), respectively, during the reaction time course. One unit of activity was defined as the amount of enzyme that was required to oxidize or reduce 1 μmol of NAD(H) per minute under the assayed conditions.

TtHBDH: the activity was measured by monitoring the consumption of 0.25 mM NADH in a mixture containing 10 mM ethyl acetoacetate (EAA) in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8.

BsADH: the activity was measured by monitoring the production of NADH in a mixture containing 25 mM ethanol and 2.5 mM NAD⁺ in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8.

Unless otherwise indicated, *SePduP* and *ΔNPduP* activities were measured by monitoring the formation of NADH in a mixture containing 10 mM propionaldehyde, 2.5 mM NAD⁺, 0.5 mM CoA, 1 mM DTT or TCEP, and 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8. A stock solution of propionaldehyde was freshly prepared.

LpNOX: the activity was measured by monitoring the consumption of 0.25 mM NADH in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8. The presence or absence of 0.15 mM FAD⁺ is indicated on the corresponding experiment.

BsGDH: the activity was measured by monitoring the production of NADH in a mixture containing 20 mM glucose and 2.5 mM NAD⁺ in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8.

Biochemical characterization of SePduP

Substrate scope: Δ NPduP activity against **2a-2m** was determined as previously described at a concentration of aldehydes of 10 mM. Taking as a reference the activity against propionaldehyde. Stock aldehyde solutions were freshly prepared.

pH profile: Activity assays were performed as previously described using 100 mM sodium acetate buffer for pH 4 and 5; sodium phosphate buffer for pH 6 to 8, and sodium bicarbonate buffer for pH 9 to 11.

Kinetic Parameters: Kinetic parameters of Δ NPduP were determined for the oxidation direction for acetaldehyde (0-100 mM), propionaldehyde (0-100 mM), butyraldehyde (0-250 mM), hexanal (0-50 mM), NAD⁺ (0-10 mM), and CoA (0-1 mM). Enzymatic assays were performed as previously described. Results were plotted and fitted to a Substrate Inhibition model (except for NAD⁺, which was fitted to a Michaelis-Menten model) through nonlinear regressions using Origin 2020 software. Stock aldehyde solutions were freshly prepared.

Thermal inactivation assays: A solution containing 0.25 U mL⁻¹ of soluble Δ NPduP was thermally inactivated at 65 °C in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 7. 50 mg of each biocatalyst was thermally inactivated at 65 °C in 0.5 mL of 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 8. Samples were withdrawn at different times, and their activity was determined with the corresponding enzymatic activity assay as previously described.

Carrier functionalization

Glyoxyl agarose (AG-G): 105 g of agarose 6 BCL were suspended in 80 mL of water, 3.4 g NaOH, 1.4 g of NaBH₄, and 36 mL of glycidol. The suspension was gently stirred for 16 h and washed with an excess of water. Then, the agarose was incubated with 1 L of 20 mM sodium periodate and gently stirred for 2 h, as previously described.^{4,5}

Cobalt chelates agarose (AG-Co²⁺): 105 g of agarose 6 BCL were suspended in 440 mL of water, 160 mL of acetone, 32.8 g NaOH, 2 g of NaBH₄, and 110 mL of epichlorohydrin. The suspension was stirred for 16 h and washed with an excess of water. Then resuspended in 2 M iminodiacetic acid at pH 11, and incubated for 20 hours, washed thoroughly, and, finally, resuspended in 30 mg mL⁻¹ CoCl₂,

vacuum filtered, and washed with an excess of water to remove the unbonded Co^{2+} .^{5, 6}

Polyethyleneimine/Polyallylamine agarose (AG-PEI or AG-PAH): AG-G was incubated with a solution of 1 mg mL^{-1} of polyallylamine (PAH) or polyethyleneimine (PEI) at pH 10, and the suspension was gently stirred for 3 h. Then, NaBH_4 was added up to 1 mg mL^{-1} and incubated for 1 h. Finally, the carrier was vacuum filtered and washed thoroughly.^{5, 7}

Trifunctional agarose (AG- Co^{2+} /G/A) was prepared through a stepwise protocol: 1) 105 g of agarose 6BCL were suspended in 440 mL of water, 160 mL of acetone, 32.8 g NaOH, 2 g of NaBH_4 , and 110 mL of epichlorohydrin. 2) The suspension was stirred for 16 h and washed with an excess of water. 3) The support was resuspended in 0.5 M iminodiacetic acid at pH 11 for 1 hour, washed thoroughly. 4) The support was resuspended in 2 M ethylenediamine at pH 11 under gentle stirring. 5) The support was washed through and then incubated with a solution of 15% glutaraldehyde and 200 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7 for 1 h. 6) The support was finally washed and resuspended in 30 mg mL^{-1} CoCl_2 , incubated for 2h, vacuum filtered, and washed with an excess of water to remove the unbonded Co^{2+} .^{5, 8}

Biocatalyst labelling with fluorophores

HB-1.3 labeling with Rhodamine B: 10 mg of an already prepared HB-1.3 was resuspended in 0.1 M sodium bicarbonate buffer at pH 8.5, containing the corresponding amount of Rhodamine B to label <5% of the immobilized enzymes, then incubated for 2.5 hours under gentle stirring at 25 °C. Then, vacuum filtered and washed thoroughly to remove the unreacted Rhodamine B with 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 7.

Enzyme Labeling with Fluorescent Probes: Fluorescent labeling of BsADH, ΔNPduP , ReTHL, TtHBDH, and EcTesB was done as reported previously.^{9, 10} Each enzyme solution in 0.1 M sodium bicarbonate buffer at pH 8.5 (BsADH: 2.24 mg mL^{-1} , ΔNPduP : 2.27 mg mL^{-1} , ReTHL: 0.8 mg mL^{-1} , TtHBDH: 4.57 mg mL^{-1} , and EcTesB: 0.4 mg mL^{-1}) was mixed with the respective fluorophore: Rhodamine B (BsADH), Atto 390 (ΔNPduP), FITC (ReTHL and EcTesB), and Alexa Fluor 647 (TtHBDH) at 1:1 molar ratio (stocks of each fluorophore were prepared in DMSO). The labeling reaction was then incubated for 2.5 h under gentle stirring at 25 °C. Later, buffer exchange and removal of unreacted fluorophores were done by filtering the enzyme solution through a tangential ultrafiltration unit (10 kDa) equilibrated in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 7.

Preparation of labeled HB-5.2: 40 mg of each HB-5.2 (ReTHL or EcTesB) were prepared as described before in the Methods section, offering the corresponding

amount of each enzyme (**Table S2**) in a molar ratio 1:5 (labeled enzyme: unlabeled enzyme), except EcTesB, which was offered 100% labeled due to the small amount offered per mass of support.

Liquid-liquid extraction of 3-hydroxybutyric acid and ¹H-NMR analysis

Once the enzyme reaction was stopped, the reaction media were recovered and adjusted to pH 3.0 with HCl, and NaCl was added to the sample until saturation. The media was transferred to a separation funnel for extraction with ethyl acetate (1:1; v:v). The mixture was gently shaken, and the ethyl acetate phase was recovered. This extraction was sequentially repeated five times. Afterwards, the organic phase was washed twice with 5 mL of distilled water. Ethyl acetate was removed and collected by rotary evaporation, and the dry sample was resuspended in MQ water for further chromatographic and H-NMR analysis. ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 500 MHz Ultra Shield spectrometer at 500 MHz. Chemical shifts were reported in parts-per-million (δ , ppm) and referenced using the residual solvent peak of deuterium oxide ($\delta = 4.79$ ppm).

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Primers to truncate the pduP gene

Primer name	Primer sequence (5'-3')
Δ NPduP_fw	AA CATATG GGCAAGGGCATTTCAGAGCGTG
Δ NPduP_rv	CAG GATCC TTAACGGATGCTAAAACCGTTGGTC

Table S2. Protein sequences of the enzymes used in this work

Protein name	Uniprot ID	Protein sequence
BsADH	P42328	MGSSHHHHHHSSGLVPRGSHMEFKRSMKAAVVEQFKEPLKIKEVEKPTISY GEVLVRIKACGVCHTDLHAAHGDPVVKPKLPLIPGHEGVGIVEEVGPGVTH LKVGDVRGIPWLYSACGHCDYCLSGQETLCEHQKNAGYSVDGGYAEYCR AAADYVVKIPDNLSEFAAIFCAGVTTYKALKVTGAKPGEWVAIYGIGGLG HVAVQYAKAMGLNVVAVDIGDEKLELAKELGADLVVNPDKEDAAMKFMKEKV GGVHAAVVTAVSKPAFQSAYNISIRRGACVLVGLPPEEMPIIFDVLNGIKII GSIVGTRKDLQEALQFAAEGKVKTIEVQPLEKINEVFDRMLKGQINGRVVLT LEDK
SePduP	Q9XDN1	MGSSHHHHHHSSGENLYFQGHMCKLKRSTSELETILRTILSEQLTTPAQT PVQPQGGKIFQSVSEIDAHAHQAFRLRYQQCPLKTRSAIISAMRQELTPLLAP LAEESANETGMGNKEDKFLKNKAALDNTPGVEDLTTTALTGDGGMVLFYYS PFGVIGSVAPSTNPTETIINNSISMLAAGNSIYFSPHPGAKKVSLLKISLIEEIA FRCCGIRNLVVTVAEPTFEATQMMMAHPRIAVLAIITGGPGIVAMGMKSGKKV IGAGAGNPPCIVDETADLVKAAEDIINGASFDYNLPCIAEKSLIVVESVAERLV QQMQTFGALLLSPADTDKLRVAVCLPEGQANKKLVGKSPSAMLEAAGIAVPA KAPRLIALVNADDPWVTSEQLMPMLPVVKVSDFDSALALALKVVEEGLHHT AIMHSQNVSRNLAAARTLQTSIFVKNGPSYAGIGVGGEGFTTFTIATPTGEG TTSARTFARSRRCVLTNGFSIR
ΔNPduP	Q9XDN1	MGSSHHHHHHSSGLVPRGSHMGKIFQSVSEIDAHAHQAFRLRYQQCPLKT RSAIISAMRQELTPLLAPLAEESANETGMGNKEDKFLKNKAALDNTPGVEDL TTTALTGDGGMVLFYYSPPFGVIGSVAPSTNPTETIINNSISMLAAGNSIYFSP HPGAKKVSLLKISLIEEIAFRCCGIRNLVVTVAEPTFEATQMMMAHPRIAVLAI TGGPGIVAMGMKSGKKVIGAGAGNPPCIVDETADLVKAAEDIINGASFDYNL PCIAEKSLIVVESVAERLVQQMQTFGALLLSPADTDKLRVAVCLPEGQANKKLV VGKSPSAMLEAAGIAVPAKAPRLIALVNADDPWVTSEQLMPMLPVVKVSD FDSALALALKVVEEGLHHTAIMHSQNVSRNLAAARTLQTSIFVKNGPSYAGIG VGGEGFTTFTIATPTGEGTTSARTFARSRRCVLTNGFSIR
AsTHL5	F1L3N8	MGSSHHHHHHSSGENLYFQGHMCKLKRSGTGMDAGKDDVYILSAVRTPIA SFRSTLTSLSAVDLGIVVTKEAIKRSLLPSSAIEETIVGNVLSAGLGQNIARQIS IASEIPKSSQCVTINKVCSSSMKAIIMGAQAIQVGYRRIVVALGSESMNAPF YVPRGEIPFGGVQLVDALQRDGLMDSIEYQPMGLCAEKTVKDYAFTREQLD AYAIESYRKAHAWKEGAFNKEVVPVSPQKRGSKVVLTEDEEYKRLIPEK VPALHPAFLKDGSGTITANASTINDGAAACVLASGEVVQEGRLKPIAKVLS YAEAGVEPIDFTVAPALAVKQLLSQSGLDEESIALWEINEAFSVTGLAFIKELR LDPKRVNVRGGAVALGHPLGASGARIVVTLVHALKSDDELGVAAICNGGGEA SAILIKKLS
ReTHL	Q0KBP1	MGSSHHHHHHSSGLVPRGSHMEFKRSMTRVVVVSGVRTAIGTFGGSLK DVAPAEALGALVREALARAQVSGDDVGHVVFVGNVIQTEPRDMLGRVAAV NGGVTINAPALTVNRLCGSGLQAIVSAQAQTILLGDTDVAIGGGAESMSRAPY LAPAARWARGMDAGLVDMMMLGALHDPFHRIHMGVTAENVAKKEYDISRAQ QDEAALESHRRASAAIKAGYFKDQIVPVVSKGRKGDVTFDTDEHVRHDATI DDMTKLRPVFVKENGTVTAGNASGLNDAAAAVMMERAEAERGLKPLAR LVSYGHAGVDPKAMGIPVPATKIALERAGLQVSDLDVIEANEAFQAQACAV TKALGLDPAKVNPNSSGISLGHPIGATGALITVKALHELNRVQGRYALVTMCI GGGQIAAIFERI
TtHBDH	Q5SIV2	MEVKRIGVVGAGQMGSGIAQVAASAGYEVVLDVAESFLERGLAAIRRLSG KFLEKGITQEAHDEALGRIRTSLSLEDLKDADLIVEAIVEDEGEKRRLFERL GALAKPEAILASNTSSIPITARYSGRPERFIGMHFFNPVPLMQLVEVIRGE LTSEATRDVVVEVARRMGTPLEVQDYPGFISNRLMMPMINEAIEALREGVA TKEAIDGIMRLGMNHPMGPLELADFIGLDTCLAIMEVLHRFGDDKYRPSPL LRRMVQAGLLGRKAGRGFYTYDEKGNKVG
EcTesB	P0AGG2	MGSSHHHHHHSSGENLYFQGHMCKLKRSSQALKNLLTLLNLEKIEEGLFRG QSEDLGLRQVFGGQVVGQALYAAKETVPEERLVHSFHSYFLRPGDSKPKPII YDVETLRDGNFSARRVAIQNGKPIFYMTASFQAPEAGFEHQKTMPSAPA PDGLPSETQIAQSLAHLPPVLKDKFICDRPLEVRPVEFHNPVKGHVAEHR QVWIRANGSVDDLRVHQYLLGYASDLNFLPVALQPHGIGFLEPGIQTIDH SMWFHRPFNLNEWLLYSVESTSASSARGFVRGEFYTDQDGLVASTVQEGV MRNHN
BsGDH	P12310	MGSSHHHHHHSSGLVPRGSHMYPDLKGVVAITGAASGLGKAMAIRFGKE QAKVVINYYSNKQDPNEVKEEVKAGGEAVVQGDVTKEEDVKNIVQTAIKE FGTLDIMINNAGLENPVPSHEMPLKDWDKVIKGTNLGTGAFSGSREAIKYFVEN DIKGNVINMSSVHEVIPWPLFVHYAASKGGIKLMTKTLALEYAPKIRVNNIG

Supporting Information

		PGAINTPINAEKFADPKQKADVESMIPMGYIGEPEEIAAVAAWLASKEASYVT GITLFADGGMTLYPSFQAGRG
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Table S3. Chemical structure of the aldehydes and alcohols tested in this work.

Alcohols	Aldehydes	
2b Propionaldehyde		
2d Hexanal		
2f Benzaldehyde		
	2h 6-hydroxyhexanal	
	2j 2-methylbutyraldehyde	
	2l 2-ethylpentanal	
	2m 2-methylhexanal	

Table S4. Kinetic Parameters of soluble enzymes

Enzyme	Reaction	K_{eq} ($\Delta G^m / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$) ^a	K_m (mM)
BsADH	Acetone + NADH = IPA + NAD	2 (-1.7)	Acetone – 5.88
			NADH – 0.0768
			IPA – 46.1
			NAD ⁺ – 0.08
	Ethanol + NAD = AcCHO + NADH	0.0015 (16.1)	Ethanol – 1.49
			NAD ⁺ – 0.08
			AcCHO – 0.034
			NADH – 0.0768
ΔNPduP	AcCHO + NAD + CoA = AcCoA + NADH	23000 (-7.7)	AcCHO – 2.943
			CoA – 0.0477
			NAD ⁺ – 0.466
			AcCoA – 0.3421
			NADH – 0.1
			AcCoA – 0.33
			AcAcCoA – 0.02
AsTHL5	2 AcCoA = AcAcCoA + CoA	0.00025 (26.3)	CoA – 0.0085
			AcCoA – 0.0258
			AcAcCoA – 0.158
			CoA – 0.1
ReTHL	2 AcCoA = AcAcCoA + CoA	0.00025 (26.3)	AcAcCoA – 0.1
			NADH – 0.0334
			3HBCoA – 0.015
			NAD ⁺ – 0.186
TtHBDH	AcAcCoA + NADH = 3HBCoA + NAD	40 (-9.3)	AcAcCoA – 0.1
			NADH – 0.0334
			3HBCoA – 0.015
EcTesB	3HBCoA -> 3-HBA + CoA	3900000 (-54.7)	3HBCoA – 0.33
	AcCoA -> Ac + CoA	1800000 (-52.7)	AcCoA – 0.2

^aValues calculated using eQuilibrator at pH 8, pMg 2, and ionic strength of 0.2 M. For COPASI model construction, water (H₂O) was omitted to simplify the models. Abbreviations: IPA-Isopropanol; AcCHO-Acetaldehyde; AcCoA: Acetyl-CoA; AcAcCoA-Acetoacetyl-CoA; 3HBCoA-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA; Ac-Acetate.

Table S5. Immobilization parameters for all individually immobilized enzymes described in this work.

Enzyme	Carrier	Immobilization Yield ^a (%)	Expressed Activity (%)	Immobilization Efficiency ^c (%)
ΔNPduP	AG-G	>99	21.5	18.0
	Co ²⁺ -Agarose	>99	8.6	8.6
	PAH-A	67	47.9	45.9
	AG-Co ²⁺ /G/A	98	8.3	8.5
BsADH	Glyoxyl-Agarose	>99	36.6	36.6
	Co ²⁺ -Agarose ^d	>99	19	19
	PEI-A	>99	99.2	99.2
	AG-Co ²⁺ /G/A ^d	>99	30	30

^a Immobilization yield (%) = $100 \times (1 - (\text{volumetric activity in the supernatant upon the immobilization} / \text{volumetric offered activity}))$. ^b Expressed activity (%) = $(\text{measured activity upon the immobilization per gram of carrier} / (\text{offered activity per mass of carrier} \times (\text{immobilization yield}/100))) \times 100$.

^c Immobilization efficiency (%) = $100 \times \text{measured activity per mass of carrier upon the immobilization} / \text{offered activity per mass of carrier}$. ^d Results obtained from Santiago-Arcos et al. 2023.⁸

Table S6. Immobilization parameters for all multi-functional heterogeneous biocatalysts described in this work.

Name	Enzyme	Chemistry	Yield ^a (%)	Apparent immobilization efficiency ^b (%)	Offered activity (U g ⁻¹)	Apparent recovered activity (U g ⁻¹)
HB-1.1	BsADH	Glyoxyl	>99	0.7	130	0.88
	ΔNPduP		99.7	0.5	23	0.12
HB-1.2	BsADH	Glyoxyl	>99	2.5	26	0.66
	ΔNPduP		99.7	1.0	23	0.22
HB-1.3	BsADH	Glyoxyl	>99	5.2	5.2-100	0.27
	ΔNPduP		99.7	2.8	23-500	0.65
HB-2	AsTHL5	Cobalt chelates	-	-	-	0.25-0.5
	TtHBDH		-	-	-	0.9-1.1
	EcTesB		-	-	-	0.3-0.5
HB-3	BsADH	Cobalt chelates	-	-	-	0.69
	ΔNPduP		-	-	-	0.1
	AsTHL5		-	-	-	0.72
	TtHBDH		-	-	-	1.3
	EcTesB		-	-	-	1.1
HB-4	ReTHL	Glyoxyl	-	9.9	6.48	0.64
	TtHBDH		-	3.25	36	1.17
	EcTesB		-	8.4	12.1	1.02
HB-5.1	BsADH	Glyoxyl	-	0.63	235	1.48
	ΔNPduP		-	0.021	540	0.12
	ReTHL		-	7.4	6.48	0.48
	TtHBDH		-	4	36	1.43
	EcTesB		-	11.7	12.1	1.42
HB-5.2	BsADH	Glyoxyl	-	0.85	142	1.2
	ΔNPduP		-	0.037	800	0.3
	ReTHL		-	1.8	5.6	0.1
	TtHBDH		-	1.6	43	0.67
	EcTesB		-	19	1.05	0.2

^a Immobilization yield (%) = 100 × (1 – (amount of protein in the supernatant upon the immobilization/offered amount of protein)). ^b Apparent immobilization efficiency (%) = 100 × apparent recovered activity/offered activity

Table S7. Kinetic functions for COPASI modelling

General reaction formula	Kinetic function	Enzymes to which the function applies
$A + B = P + Q$	$V = \frac{V_{max} \times \left(A \times B - \frac{P \times Q}{K_{eq}} \right)}{K_A \times K_B \left(\left(1 + \frac{A}{K_A} \right) \times \left(1 + \frac{B}{K_B} \right) + \left(1 + \frac{P}{K_P} \right) \times \left(1 + \frac{Q}{K_Q} \right) - 1 \right)}$	BsADH (Ethanol and Acetone), TtHBDH,
$A + B + C = P + Q$	$V = \frac{V_{max} \times \left(A \times B \times C - \frac{P \times Q}{K_{eq}} \right)}{K_A \times K_B \times K_C \left(\left(1 + \frac{A}{K_A} \right) \times \left(1 + \frac{B}{K_B} \right) \times \left(1 + \frac{C}{K_C} \right) + \left(1 + \frac{P}{K_P} \right) \times \left(1 + \frac{Q}{K_Q} \right) - 1 \right)}$	Δ NPduP
$A \rightarrow B + C$	$V = \frac{V_{max} \times A}{K_A + A}$	EcTesB (3-HB-CoA and Acetyl-CoA)
$A = B + C$	$V = \frac{V_{max} \times \left(A - \frac{P \times Q}{K_{eq}} \right)}{K_A \left(\left(1 + \frac{A}{K_A} \right) + \left(1 + \frac{P}{K_P} \right) \times \left(1 + \frac{Q}{K_Q} \right) - 1 \right)}$	ReTHL

Table S8. COPASI modelling

Model version	Enzyme	Loading (U mL ⁻¹)	Reaction conditions	Predicted 3-HBA (mM)	Predicted acetate (mM)
Model 1.0	BsADH	1 (1a)	200 mM ethanol, 300 mM acetone, 1 mM NAD ⁺ , 1 mM CoA	3.4	88
		0.7 (acetone)			
	Δ NPduP	1			
	ReTHL	1			
	TtHBDH	1			
	EcTesB	1 (5a)			
0.15 (3a)					
Model 1.1	BsADH	2.5 (1a)	200 mM ethanol, 300 mM acetone, 1 mM NAD ⁺ , 1 mM CoA	44	17.4
		1.75 (acetone)			
	Δ NPduP	10			
	ReTHL	0.25			
	TtHBDH	2.5			
	EcTesB	0.1 (5a)			
0.015 (3a)					
Model 1.2	BsADH	1 (1a)	200 mM ethanol, 300 mM acetone, 1 mM NAD ⁺ , 1 mM CoA	58	16.7
		0.7 (acetone)			
	Δ NPduP	40			
	ReTHL	0.1			
	TtHBDH	1			
	EcTesB	0.1 (5a)			
0.015 (3a)					

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Individualized reaction schemes catalyzed by the enzymes present in this work. A) Oxidation of primary alcohols by the alcohol dehydrogenase from *Bacillus stearothermophilus* (BsADH). B) Oxidative thioesterification of aldehydes by the CoA-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase from *Salmonella enterica* (SePduP). C) Non-decarboxylative Claisen condensation of acyl-CoAs by the thiolase from either *Ralstonia eutropha* (ReTHL) or *Ascaris sum* (AsTHL). D) Asymmetric reduction of acetoacyl-CoA by the 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase from *Thermus thermophilus* HB27 (TtHBDH). E) Hydrolysis of 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA by the thioesterase B from *E. coli* (EcTesB). F) Reduction of acetone by BsADH. G) Undesired hydrolysis of acyl-CoA by EcTesB.

Figure S2. SDS-PAGE of SePduP WT and Δ NPduP purification. 10 μ L of each sample were analyzed. The mass of cells lysed, and the purification procedure were the same in both purifications. Protein yields were 30 mg L_{culture}^{-1} SePduP WT, and 290 mg L_{culture}^{-1} for Δ NPduP using cultures of 3 OD (600 nm) in both cases. Abbreviations: MM (Molecular weight markers, BioRad Precision Plus Protein All Blue Standard). L (lysate), CE (soluble crude extract), FT (flow-through of the purification), W (washing buffer after flow-through), E (eluted protein), and RS (washed resin after purification).

Figure S3. Michaelis-Menten curves of Δ NPduP for different substrates and cofactors. Oxidative steady-state kinetics were calculated towards A) Acetaldehyde (0-100 mM), B) Propionaldehyde (0-100 mM), C) Butyraldehyde (0-250 mM), D) Hexanal (0-50 mM), E) NAD⁺ (0-10 mM), and CoA (0-1 mM). The activities for each substrate concentration were done in triplicate, resulting in a mean value for each substrate concentration. All mean activities were plotted and adjusted to a substrate inhibition model (except NAD⁺, which was fitted to a Michaelis-Menten model) using Origin Pro 2020 software.

Figure S4. Δ NPduP activity vs pH. Activity assays were performed as described in the Methods section. 0.1 M acetate buffer was used for pH 4 and 5; 0.1 M phosphate buffer was used for pH 6 to 8, and 0.1 M bicarbonate buffer was used for pH 9 to 11.

Figure S5. Thermal inactivation assay of Δ NPduP at 65 °C in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7.

Figure S6. Synthesis of propionyl-CoA from propionaldehyde. A) Final concentrations of propionyl-CoA or free Coenzyme A in the presence of either an excess of NAD⁺ or using NADH oxidase from *Lactobacillus pentosus* (LpNOX) with substoichiometric amounts of NAD⁺ and FAD⁺. The table on the right summarizes all entries for the different experiments represented in the plot (left). (+) indicates the presence of the corresponding compound. DTT: dithiothreitol, TCEP: tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine B) UV chromatograms (254 nm) of 1 mM of Coenzyme A (upper chromatogram); blank with 1 mM CoA, 1 mM NAD⁺, 1 mM DTT and 0.15 mM FAD⁺ (middle chromatogram); blank with 1 mM CoA and 1 mM NAD⁺ and 1 mM DTT (lower chromatogram). Peak 1 – NAD⁺; Peak 2 – Coenzyme A; Peak 3 – Coenzyme A dimer; Peak 4 – FAD⁺. C) Mass spectra of Peak 3 in blank with FAD. D) Mass spectra of Peak 2 in blank with FAD⁺. Data in panels A show the mean of two independent experiments, where the error bars represent their standard deviation.

Figure S7. Thermal inactivation assay of A) free and immobilized Δ NPduP biocatalysts at 65 °C in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 8 and B) BsADH biocatalyst at 65 °C in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 8.

Figure S8. Comparison of different NAD(H) regeneration systems towards the biosynthesis of 3-HBA from ethanol using free enzymes. The reactions were performed as described in the Methods section. Reactions contained 0.25 U mL^{-1} BsADH, 0.25 U mL^{-1} Δ NPduP, 0.05 U mL^{-1} AsTHL5, 0.1 U mL^{-1} TtHBDH and 0.05 U mL^{-1} EcTesB. Reactions containing 0.05 U mL^{-1} BsGDH also contain 100 mM glucose in the reaction media.

Figure S9. A combination of HB-2 and HB-1.2 or HB-1.1 to transform ethanol into 3-HBA. 25 mg of HB-1.2 or HB-1.1 and HB-2 were added to their corresponding reaction. Reactions were triggered by resuspending the HBs into the reaction media to a final ratio of 1/5 (w/v). The reaction media consist of 50 mM ethanol, 100 mM acetone, 1 mM CoA, 1 mM NAD⁺, and 1 mM TCEP in 0.15 M phosphate buffer, pH 8. The enzymes and their amount present on each HB are defined in Table S2.

Figure S10. A,B) Relative cofactor concentrations from different combinations of heterogeneous biocatalysts (HB) using AsTHL5 (A) or ReTHL (B) as thiolase in different biocatalysts configuration. In all reactions, 25 mg of each HB was resuspended in the reaction mixture with a ratio of 1/5 (w/v), containing 1 mM of NAD⁺ and 1 mM CoA at pH 8 and 30°C. C,D) Time-course of the cofactors during the biosynthesis of 3-HBA from ethanol catalyzed by either the combination of HB-1.3 + HB-4 (C) or by HB-5.1. Reaction was done as indicated for panels A and B. The enzymes and their amount present on each HB are defined in Table S2.

Figure S11: Epifluorescence microscopy images (left: blue channel, NADH autofluorescence; λ_{ex} : 385/30 nm; right: bright field and red channel particles labeled with Rhodamine B (RhB); λ_{ex} : 555/30 nm) tracking NADH along the reaction course. 25 mg of either a mix of HB-1.3 (labeled with RhB) and HB-4 (A), or unlabeled HB-5.1 (B) in a ratio 1/5 (w/v) of reaction mix. 5 μL samples were withdrawn from the reactor and analyzed under the microscope at 1.5, 5, and 22 hours of reaction (C). The RFU intraparticle intensity as a function of time. RFU values are the mean of 8-10 particles, and the error bars represent the corresponding standard deviation.

Figure S12: Optimization of enzyme concentration using Model 1.0. A) Parameter scan of BsADH V_{max} value. B) Parameter scan of Δ NPduP V_{max} value. C) Parameter scan of ReTHL V_{max} value. D) Parameter scan of TtHBDH V_{max} value. E) Parameter scan of EcTesB V_{max} value. The optimal V_{max} value of each enzyme is highlighted in a red circle. This value is defined as the lowest V_{max} (enzyme activity) value that yields > 95% of the maximal 3-HBA titer at 24 hours. Details of the model construction and parameter scan method are described in the Methods section.

Figure S13: Optimization of enzyme concentration using Model 1.1. A) Parameter scan of BsADH V_{max} value. B) Parameter scan of Δ NPduP V_{max} value. C) Parameter scan of ReTHL V_{max} value. D) Parameter scan of TtHBDH V_{max} value. E) Parameter scan of EcTesB V_{max} value. The optimal V_{max} value of each enzyme is highlighted with a red circle. This value is defined as the lowest V_{max} (enzyme activity) value that yields > 95% of the maximal 3-HBA titer at 24 hours. Details of the model construction and parameter scan method are described in the Methods section.

Figure S14: Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM) 40X images of HB-5.2 formed by one unlabeled enzyme (either ReTHL or EcTesB) and the left 4 enzymes labeled with compatible fluorophores; BsADH (RhB, λ_{ex} : 561 nm, orange color); Δ NPduP (Atto 390, λ_{ex} : 405 nm, blue color), either EcTesB or ReTHL (FITC; λ_{ex} : 488 nm, green color) and TtHBDH (A647, λ_{ex} : 633 nm, red color), and overlay of all fluorescence channels obtained from HB-5.2.

Figure S15: A) Pearson coefficient among the immobilized enzymes on HB-5.2, B) Relative infiltration of each enzyme through the radius of AG-G beads when co-immobilized. C) Normalized fluorescence intensity radial profile of HB-5.2 with ReTHL unlabeled. D) Normalized fluorescence intensity radial profile of the enzymes immobilized into HB-5.2 with EcTesB unlabeled. In A-D, data represent the mean value and standard deviation (error bars) of at least 15 microbeads.

Figure S16. By-products concentration produced on the reactions starting from a mix of 20 mM ethanol and either 180 mM 1-propanol or 180 mM ethylene glycol in a molar ratio of 1:10. 40 mg of HB-5.2 were used on each reaction and resuspended in the corresponding reaction mix at a ratio of 1:5 (w/v).

Figure S17. A) MS chromatograms of m/z 119.03 ± 0.02 Da of different samples. B) MS chromatograms of the 135.03 ± 0.02 Da of different samples. C) Calibration curve of 3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid. D) Calibration curve of 2,3,4-trihydroxybutyric acid (THBA). E) Mass spectra of 3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid standard at retention time 0.48 min. F) Mass spectra of the reaction at the retention time 0.48 min. G) Mass spectra of 2,3,4-trihydroxybutyric acid standard at retention time 2.5 min. H) Mass spectra of the reaction at retention time 2.5 min.

Figure S18. A) GC-MS chromatogram of the extracted Ion 84 is compatible with the double dehydration reaction of 3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid (3,4-DHBA). B) Zoom in on the GC-MS chromatogram at retention time 11.8 min. C) Mass spectra of 3,4-DHBA injection at 11.8 min. D) Mass spectra of the reaction at retention time 11.8 min.

Figure S19. A) MS chromatograms of m/z 117.05 ± 0.02 Da of different samples. B) MS chromatograms of the 131.05 ± 0.02 Da of different samples. C) Calibration curve of 3-hydroxypentanoic acid (3-HPA). D) Calibration curve of 2-methyl-3-hydroxypentanoic acid (2M3HPA). E) Mass spectra of 3-hydroxypentanoic acid standard at retention time 1.56 min. F) Mass spectra of the reaction at retention time 1.56 min. G) Mass spectra of 3-hydroxy-2-methylpentanoic standard at retention time of 2.0 min. H) Mass spectra of the reaction at retention time 2.0 min.

Figure S20. A) Time-course of the biosynthesis of 3-HBA (purple squares) and acetate (grey squares) with HB-5.2 from ethanol. Reactions were triggered by adding 3 mL of the reaction mixture (200 mM ethanol, 300 mM acetone, 0.5 mM CoASH and 2.5 mM NAD^+) to 600 mg of HB-5.2 in a ratio of 1/5 (w/v). Reaction was incubated at 30°C. Samples of the suspension were withdrawn over time, filtered, and analyzed as indicated in the Methods section. B) 3-HBA (Purple) and acetate (grey) titer and STY (light purple) regarding 3-HBA at different flow rates and reaction conditions as described in panel A. Acetate/3-HBA molar ratio is represented in black dots.

Figure S21. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of isolated products through liquid-liquid extraction from the outcome solution of the PBR.

Figure S22. A) SDS-PAGE analysis of fresh and used HB-5.2, both in batch and in flow. Lane 1: Offered enzyme mix to AG-G. Line 2: Supernatant of the immobilization. Line 3: New HB-5.2. Line 4: HB-5.2 after 7 reaction cycles. Line 5: Inlet section of HB-5.2 after 25 days in flow. Line 6: Medium section of HB-5.2 after 25 days in flow. Line 7: Outlet section of HB-5.2 after 25 days in flow. Line 8 Molecular Weight Markers. B) Relative recovered activity of each enzyme on different samples of HB-5.2. The initial apparent activity of each enzyme after immobilization was taken as 100%.

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